

RETHINKING THE CONCEPT OF «LIFE CYCLE» IN RUSSIAN POSTMODERN LITERARY

Gizdulin Eldar Fatihovich

lecturer, Fergana State University

Arslonova Mekribonu Tavakkal kizi

Lecturer, Fergana State University

Yuldosheva Dilnoza Tojiali kizi

Lecturer, Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11515428>

Abstract: This article analyzes the early work of A. Bitov with an emphasis on rethinking the concept of the "life cycle". The authors explore how the concept of the "life cycle" is embodied and developed in the works of the writer, revealing its significance and evolution in the context of literary creativity.

Keywords: A. Bitov, early creativity, life cycle, reinterpretation, literary analysis.

The life cycle is initially a biological concept that designates the process of birth, development, aging and death of various species of animals and plants within the Earth's biosphere, determined by the natural parameters of the ecological environment. The life cycle can be interpreted as a continuous adaptation system that ensures the continuity of the existence of species in space and time. As time and science evolve, the life cycle is used in all fields of knowledge, including science and academia, the socio-economic sphere, software, and other arts. Philosophically, Heraclitus wrote about "cycles" as early as the 6th century BC. According to him, "The world is an eternally living fire, but it has always been, is and will always be an eternally living fire, steadily igniting and steadily fading." This aphorism illustrates the whole process of life well. According to Heraclitus, the world is eternal and unchangeable, but the course of nature's development is cyclical; In nature, everything changes every moment, either inheriting the essence of what came before it and continuing its properties, or inheriting its offal or becoming its opposite, but life as a whole is a process.

In literature, writers tend to associate the life cycle with the concepts of life and death. Russian Russian literary tradition actually originates from Pushkin, after whom Russian writers consciously combined their reflections on life and death in their works, according to D. Merezhkovsky. The life cycle in Bitov's work mainly manifests itself as a continuation of the value of life. In his early works, the characters are mainly children or minors, who, despite their fragility and incompleteness of perception of the world, are also representatives

of the most real and immaculate life. These characters are often accompanied by characters who have matured or are coming to the end of their lives. The author intentionally depicts images of adults and children together, intending to emphasize the phenomenon of the relay race of the life cycle.

In the story "The Big Ball", a little girl wandered into an unfamiliar place in search of a magic ball. In the courtyard of a short alley, Tonya met an old woman who was also standing in line for balloons, and listened to her story about the past. The old man's hope turned into a soap bubble, the symbol of a new life is finally given to Tonya, she finally got a balloon and fell asleep in the company of her father. And only Tonya knows this magical place — that's exactly the hope Bitov leaves for the reader. In the story "Jubilee", the old man Boris Karlovich, who felt suffocated by the rigidity of his life, took refuge on a bench in a small park to avoid the anniversary. Looking at the children full of vitality, Boris thought to himself that he should raise them and hope that they would be different. That they will be able to live like humans for a little longer than just in childhood. Children are a symbol of vibrant life and free will, unlike the elderly, who represent adults locked in rigid ceremonial rituals. The old man hopes that the children will serve as a spark for the continuation of human life.

They are a new force full of hope, a driving force for the continuation of civilization and the renewal of the spiritual core, which is the will to lifelong inheritance. Seryozha in the "Suburban area", as an adult who has lost the meaning of life, gradually sinks into stupor and emptiness from everyday chores. He constantly searches for the meaning of life, but does not find it until he acquires a taste and sensitivity to life in intimacy with his son, where he is amazed at the innocent simplicity of his son and finds the truth, approaching the truth of the primitive and faith. In the person of his son, Sergei learns the true meaning of life and simple happiness. Here the author disappears, and only the reader and the main character remain, resonating with each other. The stream of life begins to flow quietly between father and son, and the transmission of life ends at this moment, is inherited, develops, and the value of life continues.

Maturity, aging, and death are processes that bring life to an end, but in a cultural sense, death is not the end of life, but the beginning of something else. The stories of the Beats do not end in tragedy, but inspire hope. Children are a sign of continuity and the beginning of a new life cycle. The end of one cycle of life symbolizes the beginning of a new round of life. What is life after death? It is a rebirth that inherits the original will and legacy. In the article "My grandfather Chekhov and great-grandfather Pushkin", Bitov is convinced that 60 years after

Pushkin's death Chekhov was born, and by age Chekhov could have been his grandfather, which is not a coincidence, but a sign of the life cycle. According to the Eastern calendar, 60 years is a cycle of reincarnation. Consequently, "by age, Pushkin could have been Chekhov's grandfather, as Chekhov was mine." Russian Russian culture was not destroyed by Pushkin's death, it was transmitted by such literary giants as Chekhov, and in the same way Chekhov's death did not interrupt the Russian cultural tradition, it was passed down from generation to generation by writers such as Bitov. This is the true meaning of the life cycle

Reference:

1. Bitov A. My grandfather Chekhov and great-grandfather Pushkin. Autobiography // Literature. 2004. № 36 (612). URL: <https://lit.1sept.ru/article.php?ID=200403603>.
2. Bitov A.G. The Big Balloon. M., 1963.
3. Bitov A.G. Dacha locality (Double). St. Petersburg, 1999.
4. Tsurkan V.V. The concept "childhood" in the early work of Andrei Bitov (to the anthology of artistic concepts) // Problems of History, Philology, Culture. 2011. № 3. C. 731-734

